

Time-Dependent Schrodinger Equation, Flux and Force

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In this note, we consider the time-dependent Schrodinger equation in terms of derivatives of time and spatial flux. We also try to examine the role of force and “acceleration” in the time-dependent case. Finally, we consider a few ideas related to a time-dependent oscillator with the additional potential, $x f(t)$.

Time-Independent Case

In a previous note, it was argued that the form $\exp(ipx)$ is the starting point for the time-independent Schrodinger case. This, it seems, represents two channels $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$ which average separately and exchange probability in a periodic manner. If such a particle is placed in a region with a potential $V(x)$, it was argued there would be scattering at different x points, yielding a time-independent conditional probability: $\langle p \exp(ipx) / W(x) \rangle$ where $W(x)$, a normalization constant, is called the wavefunction. $W(x)$ has the property that it transforms under $x \rightarrow x + b$ (b infinitesimal) like $\exp(ipx)$ with p replaced by $\langle p \text{ conditional average} \rangle$ where:

$$\langle p \text{ conditional} \rangle = [\text{Sum over } p \quad p \exp(ipx) \exp(ipx)] / W(x) = d/dx W(x) / W(x) = u(x) = \text{spatial flux}$$

$$\langle p^2 \text{ conditional} \rangle = [\text{Sum over } p \quad p^2 \exp(ipx) \exp(ipx)] / W(x) = - d^2/dx^2 W(x) / W(x)$$

For the time dependent case, we argue $W(x,t)$ should transform in the same manner as above for $x \rightarrow x+b$ except with p replaced with $f(p,t)$, and transform like $\exp(iEt)$ with E replaced with E conditional average for $t \rightarrow t+b$ where:

$$\begin{aligned} \langle E \text{ conditional} \rangle = E(x,t) &= [\text{Sum over } E \quad g(E,x) \exp(iEt)] / W(x,t) = -i d/dt W(x,t) / W(x,t) \\ &= -i \text{ time flux} = -i \quad uT(x,t) \end{aligned}$$

It is possible to obtain $E(x,t)$ using $\langle p^2/2m \text{ conditional} \rangle$ and if one insists the two be the same, one obtains the time-dependent Schrodinger equation i.e.:

$$-i d/dt W(x,t) / W(x,t) = -1/2m d/dx d/dx W(x,t) / W(x,t) + V(x,t) \quad ((2))$$

Note the “classical kinetic energy term” $-1/2m d/dx d/dx W(x,t) / W(x,t) = .5m v(x,t)v(x,t)$ is now time dependent and $E(x,t)$ is no longer constant, either in space or time.

Flux Considerations

It seems the time-dependent Schrodinger equation may be thought of entirely in terms of time and spatial flux.

For both cases, spatial density is $W^*(x,t)W(x,t)$.

We immediately have the result:

$$d/dx [uT(x,t)] = d/dt u(x,t) \text{ Here } d/dx \text{ and } d/dt \text{ are partial derivatives } ((1))$$

and $E(x,t) = d/dt [-i uT(x,t)]$. Also, note that $u(x,t) = \langle i p \text{ conditional} \rangle$.

Thus, the time-dependent Schrodinger equation seems to be equivalent to:

$$d/dx E(x,t) = d/dt \langle p \text{ conditional} \rangle ((2 b))$$

Consider a spatial density independent of time i.e. $W^*(x,t)W(x,t) = g(x)$. Now:

$$d/dx W^*(x,t)W(x,t) = W^*(x,t)W(x,t) [u(x,t) + u^*(x,t)]$$

If $u(x,t)$ depends explicitly on time, then density would not be constant in time, so $u(x,t) = u(x)$.

$W^*(x,t)W(x,t)$ suggests $W(x,t) = \exp(i E(t)) W(x)$. From ((1)):

$d/dx E(x,t) = d/dt u(x,t) = 0$ so $E(t)$ also, but this must be a constant E in space from ((1)).
(i.e. multiply both sides by d/dt and switch the order of the derivatives.)

Considerations of Force

Starting with ((1))

$$\begin{aligned} -i d/dt u(x,t) &= d/dx E(x,t) = d/dx [-1/2m d/dx d/dx W(x,t) / W(x,t) + V(x,t)] \\ &= -F(x,t) + [1/2m d/dx d/dx W(x,t) / W(x,t)] u(x,t) + (-1/2m) 1/W(x,t) [d/dx]^3 W(x,t) \end{aligned} ((3))$$

It should be noted that for the time-independent case, the last two terms on the RHS cancel with $-F(x,t)$ i.e. $d/dt u(x,t) = 0$. Thus, for the time dependent case, there is a portion of minus force $-F(x,t)$ left. This piece seems to create an acceleration type of term i.e.:

$$-i d/dx E(x,t) = i d/dt \langle p \text{ conditional} \rangle \text{ where } d/dt \text{ is the partial derivative. } ((4))$$

This almost has the appearance of Newton's second law.

Example of Harmonic Oscillator with Additional $x f(t)$ Potential

This example has been discussed in detail in (1) and (2). The time-dependent Schrodinger equation is:

$$-i \frac{d}{dx} W(x,t) = -\frac{1}{2m} \frac{d^2}{dx^2} W(x,t) + .5k x^2 W(x,t) + x f(t) W(x,t) \quad ((5))$$

In (1), the problem is solved by using:

$$W(x,t) = \exp(-i E_n t) \exp(i b(t) y) W_n(y) \exp(i c(t)) \quad ((6))$$

Where $y = x - b(t)$, $\frac{d}{dt} b(t) = y f(t) - k b(t) y$ and $W_n(y)$ is the solution of the time-independent Schrodinger equation (with x replaced by y) and $E_n = \sqrt{k/m} (n+.5)$.

This is a time-dependent problem, but given that x^2 approaches infinity as x approaches infinity (as long as it is not canceled by $x f(t)$) one might expect $W(x,t)$ should be damped i.e. approach 0 for large x . Thus, one has the appearance of a trapped or bound state type problem. Consider fluxes for the case of $n=0$ i.e. $W_n(y) = \exp[-.5 \sqrt{k/m} (x-b(t)(x-b(t)))]$

$$u(x,t) = -\sqrt{k/m}(x-b(t)) + i b(t) \text{ which is complex.}$$

$$E(x,t) = i c(t) + \sqrt{k/m} (x-b(t)) \frac{d}{dt} b(t) + i (x \frac{d}{dt} b(t) + 2 b \frac{d}{dt} b(t)) \text{ also complex.}$$

One sees that ((1)) $\frac{d}{dt} u(x,t) = \frac{d}{dx} u_T(x,t)$ is satisfied.

In this problem, $\frac{d}{dx} E(x,t) = \sqrt{k/m} \frac{d}{dt} b(t) + i \frac{d}{dt} b(t) = \frac{d}{dt} u(x,t)$.

Thus, $\frac{d}{dx} W^*(x,t)W(x,t) = W^*(x,t)W(x,t) [u(x,t) + u^*(x,t)]$ changes in time. The real portion of the spatial flux causes density to change in time. Density is given here by:

$$C^*C \exp([\sqrt{k/m} (x-b(t))(x-b(t))]) \text{ where } C \text{ is a normalization constant.}$$

In (1), the strategy of solving ((5)) is to obtain a time-independent Schrodinger equation. First, the transformation $y=x-b(t)$ is used. This leads to:

$\frac{d}{dt} W(y,t) = -i \frac{d}{dy} W(y) \frac{d}{dt} b(t) + H(y) W(y)$ where $H(y)$ is the Hamiltonian written in terms of y . The first term on the RHS is part of the time flux.

This allows part of the time flux to cancel with part of the spatial flux when one uses: $W(x,t) = \exp(i b(t) y) W(y)$. Even though $y(x,t)$, it is treated as an independent variable when one applies $-i d/dt W(y,t)$. (see (2) for details). $\exp(i b(t) y)$ also leads to the elimination of $y f(t) W(y,t)$ leaving only a pure time dependent potential piece which may be removed by adding $\exp(i c(t))$ as a factor to $W(y,t)$.

From this note, ((1)) $d/dx E(t,x) = d/dt u(t,x)$ suggests that if one can have a spatial flux which is independent of time, one may have $E(x,t) = E$. The cancellation of portions of time and spatial fluxes seems to achieve this. (In addition, the portion $y f(t)$ is eliminated.) $W(y)$ leads to a spatial flux $d/dy W(y) / W(y)$ that appears as if it is independent of t (although t is hidden in $y=x-b(t)$).

Conclusion

It seems the Schrodinger time-dependent equation may be obtained by imposing the condition that $W(x,t)$ be a function which changes like $\exp(iEt - ikx)$ except that E and p are replaced $\langle E \text{ conditional} \rangle = -i d/dt W(x,t)$ and $\langle i p \text{ conditional} \rangle = d/dx W(x,t)$. One then imposes an equality of energy obtained using $\langle p^2/2m \text{ conditional} \rangle + V(x,t)$ and $\langle E \text{ conditional} \rangle$. In addition, it seems the time-independent case, there is a relationship between time and spatial flux:

$$d/dx uT(x,t) = d/dt u(x) \quad \text{where } uT(x,t) = d/dt W(x,t) / W(x,t) \text{ and } u(x,t) = d/dx W(x,t) / W(x,t)$$

Furthermore, $-i d/dx uT(x,t) = E(x,t)$ and $u(x) = \langle i p \text{ conditional} \rangle$ so one has a kind of Newton's second law equation:

$$d/dx E(x,t) = - d/dt \langle p \text{ conditional} \rangle \quad \text{where } d/dx \text{ and } d/dt \text{ are partial derivatives.}$$

References

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